

Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal (EIIRJ)

Impact Factor : 0.987

ISSN : 2277-8721

***Reviewed Online Journal
(Bi-Monthly)
Mar-April ISSUES***

Chief-Editor:

Ubale Amol Baban

www.aarhat.com

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

CiteFactor
Academic Scientific Journals

2015

PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS AND TEACHERS OF SECONDARY STAGE ON RELEVANCE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF VALUE EDUCATION AND THEIR IMPLEMENTATION

Mr. Sangeet Sharma

Assistant Professor
IVS, Affiliated to GGSIPU
New-Delhi

Ms. Amandeep Kaur

Assistant Professor
MIMT
G. Noida

Abstract

Value Education is of utmost importance especially in the present scenario and it consists of developing the right balanced feelings and emotions. According to National Curriculum for Primary and Secondary Education (1985), the crisis of values our society is passing through “demands more explicit and deliberate educational efforts towards value development”. The objectives of the study were: (1) To study the need and significance of value education (2) To study the awareness of students on the significance of value Education (3) To study the perception of teachers on various ways through which value education can be imparted. The sample of the study comprised of 40 students studying in Class IX and X and 10 Teachers from 10 schools of Delhi. The tools used were: Close-ended questionnaire and open ended questionnaires. The findings indicated that more than average number of students are aware of the significance of value education but they need to practice and understand the practicing ways through which they can impart values to the students. The Teachers suggested various ways through which we can impart value education to students in a long lasting and effective manner.

Keywords: *Perception of students and Teachers, Significance of Value Education*

Introduction

Value Education is of paramount importance and in today's time where there is dire need of values for balancing the minds of young children and society at large. The concept of values deals with the understanding of the moral ethics and norms in personal and social aspects of our lives.

Values can best be inculcated and transacted through the means of Education. There are various ways through which we can inculcate values in students. Education does not just mean teaching the students how to read and write, but also includes developing the personality of the students to make him or her an ideal person and a humane personality. So value education is education in values and education towards the inculcation of values.

Need of the Study

Values marks the main foundation for a balanced personality in any individual, but especially at the adolescent stage, values need to be inculcated in them for their right conduct

.There are many incidents of violence, extreme behavior and also tendencies of adolescent children to suicide or harm themselves. All this happens when there is no such balance in their personalities. Value Education should be promoted in students for developing their balanced personalities.

According to the UNESCO (1972) report the “teacher's duty is less and less to inculcate and more and more to encourage thinking, his formal functions apart, he will have to become more and more an adviser, a partner to talk to someone who helps seek out conflicting arguments rather than handing our readymade truths. He will have to devote more time and energy to productive and creative activities; interaction, discussion, stimulation, understanding encouragement.”

Moreover, there are various ways through which we can inculcate and make understand the concept of value education to the students and that to understanding the perception of teachers, gives a glimpse of transacting and making the students value oriented individuals.

Objectives:

1. To study the need and significance of value education
2. To study the awareness of students on the significance of value Education
3. To study the perception of Teachers on various ways through which value education can be imparted.

Sample

The sample of the study comprised of 40 students and 10 Teachers randomly selected from 10 schools of Delhi.

Tools

1. Close-ended questionnaire
2. Open ended questionnaires.

Procedure of Data Collection

10 schools were chosen for collecting the data wherein 4 students and 1Teacher from respective school were selected randomly for conducting the research.

Analysis and Interpretation

Close ended questionnaire for students for knowing the need and significance of value education and awareness of students on the significance of value Education. 77% students were of this opinion that they are aware of the concept of value education and its importance in today's time. They were of this view that they know about Values and its importance of

